

Electrical Energy from Bacteria using MFC (Microbial Fuel Cells) Technology
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Electrical energy is the primary energy that exists in the world and plays a very important role in human life. The technology discovered almost entirely uses electrical energy to support its use. The rapid growth and development of population that occurs in the world must be in line with the increasing need and availability of primary energy in the world, one of which is electrical energy. This certainly happens in Indonesia because the population in Indonesia continues to increase. According to his estimates, electrical energy in Indonesia will continue to increase by 4.6% every year, apart from that by 2030 there will be a threefold increase compared to before. This results in the need for a new supply of renewable fuel, which functions as an alternative energy source to produce renewable electrical energy and of course must be environmentally friendly (Dewi et al., 2008). One alternative for producing electrical energy is to utilize microorganisms using MFC (Microbial Fuel Cell) technology. MFC (Microbial Fuel Cell) is a bio-electrochemical technology that uses microbial activity to convert chemical energy contained in organic substrates into electrical energy (Idris et al., 2016). This MFC (Microbial Fuel Cell) system can use waste water which is later processed and produces electrical energy, making it an environmentally friendly device and has dual benefits, namely bioelectricity generation and waste management (Xu et al., 2017; Zheng et al., 2015). There are several reasons why this topic is important to discuss because apart from producing alternative energy from microorganisms, MFC can also reduce the waste burden and efficiently use resources (Ibrahim et al., 2017).

There has been a lot of previous research discussing MFC (Microbial Fuel Cell), not only using organic liquid waste in this technology, but also using other potential sources. As in Utami et al., 2019 who studied the potential of peat water as a source of electrical energy using Microbial Fuel Cell (MFC) technology. Khafidiyanto et al., 2017 explained about the use of liquid fruit waste in MFC technology by utilizing simple organic material (glucose) in fruit waste to be used as nutrition for bacteria. Kurniawati et al., 2017 explained the use of MFC (Microbial Fuel Cell) by knowing the potential electrical energy produced from the leachate processing process using an evapotranspiration system and knowing the level of efficiency of COD processing in leachate using sente plants. Kurniawan et al., 2022 explained the knowledge spread into one article about

the performance of MFC in optimizing electricity generation from wastewater containing phosphorus (P), while simultaneously removing target nutrients from wastewater.

Of the several types of existing research, there are many studies that explain the use of liquid waste in Microbial Fuel Cell (MFC) technology, one of the aims of which is to reduce pollution in the environment. One potential source that can be used in MFC technology is compost. Organic waste such as vegetable waste can be processed by composting. Compost is an organic fertilizer, organic fertilizer is very widely used because it has good benefits for the environment, soil and also for plants. Compost really helps solve problems in the environment and compost can also add nutrients and improve the structure and texture of the soil and can store water (Febria et al., 2021). The processed compost products can be used in Compost Solid Phase Microbial Fuel Cells (CSMFCs) technology, which is a composting technology that is integrated with the MFCs system to produce compost and produce bioelectricity from organic solid waste (Ariyanti et al., 2019). With this research, it is proven that MFC can not only work on organic liquid waste but can also utilize the results of processing organic waste such as compost. Apart from that, composting will have an increasingly positive impact on soil quality, and supported by sufficient nutrients, plants will produce optimal production (Rich et al., 2017). According to Chen et al., (2019), by decomposing in an open environment, organic fertilizer can form by itself. Apart from compost. Apart from using organic waste, what is even more interesting is that MFC technology can use sediment. According to Febria et al., 2020, electricity can be generated using a Sediment Microbial Fuel Cell (SMFC). Where the presence of microbes in the sediment is able to change organic material to produce electrons, this is proven by the production of electric current reaching its peak on the 20th day with a value of 432.69 mA/m². MFC is a technology that utilizes microbes in an organic medium to convert organic materials into electrical energy. The nature of microbes that can degrade the organic medium (enrichment media) in MFC produces electron and proton ions so that these ions produce differences in electrical potential (Hutapea., 2019). According to Deng et al., 2020, there are many microorganisms that play a role in MFC, some are aerobes, facultative anaerobes, and even obligate anaerobes. The advantages of using MFC are that MFC has a high level of efficiency, soft operating conditions, no energy input required, and can be applied in various places with inadequate infrastructure (Gomez Vidales et al., 2019). MFC can also utilize microorganisms found in sediment to degrade organic material (Song et al., 2020). Marine sediments are known to have an important role as a source of organic material for marine

vegetation and have the potential to produce new chemical compounds originating from various biological activities (Poliakova et al., 2017).

Microbial Fuel Cell (MFC) technology is very important to discuss because it has great potential in producing renewable and environmentally friendly electrical energy. MFCs can use various resources, such as organic liquid waste, compost, and sediment, to produce electrical energy. Apart from that, this technology can also reduce waste burden and increase resource use efficiency. Various studies have discussed the use of MFC, including the use of organic liquid waste, compost and sediment, as well as the potential for electrical energy produced from the waste processing process. This conclusion shows that MFCs have great potential in improving the quality of life and reducing environmental impacts, and require further research to increase the efficiency and scale of production of the electrical energy produced.

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